

FAILURE MECHANISMS IN GLASS FILLED

EPOXY RESIN COMPOSITES

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The variation of crack velocity (V) with stress intensity factor (K_I) at the tip of a crack has been measured for an epoxy resin containing 46% by volume of irregularly-shaped silica particles. It has been found that at crack velocities above 10^{-6} m sec⁻¹ the crack propagates primarily through the silica particles, whereas at velocities below this value failure occurs primarily by particle pull-out. This variation in fracture mode is accompanied by a corresponding change in slope of the $V(K)$ curve. Using data obtained from creep rupture experiments and the derived $V(K)$ relationship it has been possible to estimate the size of the inherent flaw in the composite. It is approximately twice the average particle diameter which is also equal to the size of the largest particles (~ 140 μm). Fracture of the unfilled epoxy resin and the effect of environment upon slow crack growth in the composite have also been investigated.

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Introduction

The design of structural components requires a thorough knowledge of the properties of the engineering material and the pertinent failure criterion for that load bearing member. A fracture mechanics approach is frequently used as a failure criterion for high strength materials where the plane strain fracture toughness, K_{IC} , defines the onset of brittle (unstable) fracture of the material. The fracture toughness, K_{IC} , of a material is dependent on the microstructural features and is generally insensitive to the chemical species in the surrounding environment. However, under certain stress and environmental conditions, imperfections or flaws in a structural material can slowly extend and lead to a time-dependence on fracture stress. The successful exploitation of the engineering material therefore requires a detailed understanding of the time-dependent failure characteristics of the material so that accurate failure predictions can be made.

Fracture involves two time-sensitive processes; (1) crack initiation and (2) crack propagation. The structural life-time of a component can therefore be considered simply as the sum of the times for completion of the two stages of fracture. This means that

$$\psi_f = \psi_i + \psi_p \quad (1)$$

where ψ_f is the time-to-failure, and ψ_i and ψ_p are the times to initiate and propagate a crack to some critical size, respectively, at which point catastrophic fracture occurs. Cracking can therefore commence at a value of $K_I < K_{IC}$ where K_I is the stress intensity factor describing the state of stress at the crack tip. (The subscript I refers to the crack opening mode of failure). The threshold value of K_I at which cracking starts (designated K_I^*) depends to a large extent on the level of applied stress and the environmental conditions; it does not ordinarily rely entirely on the properties of the material. Under conditions leading to sub-critical crack growth at $K_I < K_{IC}$, the dynamics of crack propagation can be described uniquely by the stress intensity factor, K_I , at the crack tip and a corresponding crack velocity, V , ($= da/dt$ under constant stress), shown schematically in Fig. 1. The curve may in general be divided into three regions of crack growth; regions I and II result from the effects of a stress and environment, whilst region III represents mainly mechanical failure and is essentially independent of the environment.

There is currently considerable interest in understanding the toughening mechanisms in brittle materials modified by the inclusion of second phase brittle particles (1-8). Experimental work has centred upon measuring the toughness of the composite as a function of the particle volume fraction (1-4,6,8,9) and surface treatment of the particles (3,8,9) during fast (unst-

able) crack propagation. In general, the stiffness of the silica particle-epoxy resin composite is higher than that of the pure epoxy resin (10) and also the composite normally has a higher fracture toughness than the unreinforced resin (1-3).

In this present investigation we have studied slow (stable) crack growth in an epoxy resin containing 46% by volume of silica particles where the surface treatment of the silica has been kept constant. This material has been found to suffer from subcritical crack growth and the variation of crack velocity (V) with stress intensity factor (K_I) at the tip of the crack has been measured using a Double Torsion (DT) specimen developed for brittle ceramics (11,12). This test enables the $V(K)$ relationship to be evaluated rapidly over a range of crack velocities between approximately 10^{-2} m sec $^{-1}$ and 10^{-10} m sec $^{-1}$ using a load relaxation technique that does not require direct observation of the moving crack. This approach has enabled microfailure processes in the composite to be studied as a function of crack velocity. By constructing $V(K)$ diagrams it has been possible to accurately predict the times-to-failure of specimens loaded to stresses below those required to initiate fast catastrophic fracture; also a model has been proposed to explain the microscopic fracture behaviour of this kind of composite material. The DT specimen can be easily used in wet and dry environments and the effect of water upon crack propagation in the composite has also been studied.

Experimental

Materials and test conditions

The material investigated was a silica-filled epoxy resin composite supplied in the form of 7mm thick sheets by Ciba-Geigy Ltd. The epoxy resin was CT 200 cured with HT 901 hardener and filled with Z 300 silica flour. This flour consisted of irregularly-shaped silica particles and sieve analysis showed that over 50% of the particles were in the range 64 - 74 μ m. The ratio of epoxy resin:hardener:filler was 100:30:200 parts by weight; densities of 1.23 gm/cc for the epoxy resin and 2.2 gm/cc for the silica give a volume fraction of silica of about 46%. The composite has been cured at 135 $^{\circ}$ C for 16 hours. A sample of CT 200 epoxy resin cured under similar conditions with HT 901 hardener in the ratio of 100:30 parts by weight but without the silica flour was also examined.

Most tests were carried out in air at 20 ± 2 $^{\circ}$ C with a relative humidity of $60 \pm 10\%$. Some preliminary experiments were carried out to investigate the effect of environment using distilled water and paraffin both at 20 ± 2 $^{\circ}$ C.

Specimen design and analysis

Double-torsion (DT) specimens were machined from the sheets of material in the form of 75 mm by 30 mm rectangular plates. The specimens were edge-notched at one end and a V-shaped groove was machined from the notch along one face of each specimen. In the DT test the sample is supported on two parallel rollers, with the centre-groove on the bottom face, and loaded using two hemispheres at the notched end (Fig. 2). A crack is forced to propagate at the root of the notch and is guided by the shallow groove (see the shaded portion in Fig. 2). It can be shown (11,12) that the stress intensity factor, K_I , at the crack tip is independent of crack length in the DT specimen and for an elastic material is given by:

$$K_I = P W_m \left(\frac{3(1 + \nu)}{W t^3 t_n} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad (2)$$

where P is the applied load, W_m is the moment arm, ν is Poisson's ratio, W is the bar width, t is the bar thickness, and t_n is the plate thickness in the plane of the crack.

Constant displacement (load relaxation) method

If the plate is loaded and held at constant displacement ($dy/dt = 0$), the crack growth rate ($da/dt = V$) is given by (11);

$$\frac{da}{dt} = V = - \frac{P_{i,f}}{P^2} \left(a_{i,f} + \frac{C}{B} \right) \left(\frac{dP}{dt} \right)_y \quad (3)$$

where $P_{i,f}$ is the initial (or final) load, P is the instantaneous load, $a_{i,f}$ is the initial (or final) crack length, and B and C are constants relating to the slope and intercept of a compliance analysis calibration curve for the DT specimen, $(y/p) f(a)$, respectively.

The crack velocity can therefore be found directly from the rate of load relaxation $(dP/dt)_y$, providing the initial or final values of load ($P_{i,f}$) and crack length ($a_{i,f}$) are known, and providing the material does not suffer from mechanical relaxation due to, for example, molecular rearrangements in the arms of the DT specimen. This source of error can be reduced by pre-loading the sample to P^* (or K_I^*)[†] for about 15 minutes before carrying out the experiment. By this means, some of the molecular relaxation can be eliminated before carrying out the load relaxation test.

[†] P^* (or K_I^*) is the value of load (or stress intensity factor) below which no crack growth can be observed ($V < 10^{-10}$ m sec⁻¹).

Observations of the crack front profile during crack propagation show that the crack extends further along the lower face than the upper face. The crack velocity is therefore smaller than given by equation (3) by an amount determined by the ratio $\Delta a/b$ where Δa is the difference between the crack length measured along the top and bottom faces of the DT specimen, and b is the width of the crack (11). Thus, equation (3) becomes;

$$V = -\phi \frac{P_{i,f}}{P^2} \left(a_{i,f} + \frac{C}{B} \right) \left(\frac{dP}{dt} \right)_y \quad (4)$$

where $\phi = b/(\Delta a^2 + b^2)^{\frac{1}{2}}$. For 7 mm thick epoxy ϕ equals 0.4. At any particular value of crack velocity, the stress intensity factor may be calculated from the instantaneous load, P , and specimen dimensions using equation (2).

Constant load method

If the plate is loaded to a constant load ($dP/dt = 0$), the crack growth rate can be calculated providing the initial and final values of crack length ($a_{i,f}$) are known and also the time interval between obtaining these two measured values, i.e. $V = (\Delta a/\Delta t)_P$. The stress intensity factor may be calculated from the constant applied load, P , using equation (2). This experimental approach is particularly useful for obtaining $V(K)$ information at low crack speeds in visco-elastic materials and therefore the test method can be repeated several times on the same specimen. The load relaxation method for visco-elastic materials can lead to erroneous results at long times (low values of crack velocity) and therefore this latter approach provides a check on the former method as well as obtaining crack velocities as a function of K .

Constant displacement rate method

Under constant displacement rate conditions, $\left(\frac{dy}{dt} \right) = \text{constant}$, the crack propagates at a constant load, P , (or K_I). It can be shown that (11)

$$\left(\frac{dy}{dt} \right) = B P \left(\frac{da}{dt} \right) = BPV \quad (5)$$

where B is a constant related to the slope of a compliance calibration curve for the material.

Procedure

The test device that is illustrated schematically in Fig. 2

was used in an Instron loading machine. In order to calculate K_{Ic} from equation (2), we have assumed the Poisson's ratio (ν) of epoxy resin to be 0.25 and for the filled system ν has been taken as 0.27.

All three methods of measuring crack velocity were employed although most of the data was obtained using the load relaxation method. The analysis assumes that the load relaxation is due entirely to crack growth; however, in viscoelastic materials load relaxation will take place in the arms of the DT specimen because of the time-dependence of modulus. This would therefore give rise to an overestimation of the crack velocity. In the present investigation we have reduced this source of error by pre-loading the specimens to a value of K_{Ic} where the crack velocity was very low ($< 10^{-10}$ m sec $^{-1}$). The load is held constant for about 15 minutes to allow load relaxation in the arms to take place. The specimen was then loaded at a cross-head speed of the order of 10 mm min $^{-1}$ to a value of K_{Ic} where the crack growth rate was appreciable ($\sim 10^{-3}$ m sec $^{-1}$) and the load relaxation test continued in the manner described earlier. The load relaxation method permitted several experiments to be carried out upon the same specimen which tended to reduce the inherent scatter. The good agreement between the crack velocities measured using the load relaxation method and crack velocities obtained by the other two methods confirmed confidence in the load relaxation techniques.

Fractography

Fracture surfaces of typical specimens were examined in a Stereoscan scanning electron microscope. The surfaces were prepared for observation by depositing thin layers (~ 100 Å) of carbon and gold-palladium alloy onto the fracture surfaces.

Results

Constant displacement-rate tests

The fracture of the unreinforced epoxy resin was investigated using the constant displacement-rate method. The material showed discontinuous cracking with the crack jumping at intervals through the specimen. Figure 3a shows a load-time curve for the epoxy resin and the peak values of load correspond to values of K_{Ic} of $0.85 + 0.05$ MNm $^{-3/2}$. Phillips and Scott (13) found similar behaviour for other types of epoxy resins fractured using the DT specimen; in some cases, however, they observed continuous cracking depending upon the curing cycle.

The load-time curves from constant displacement-rate tests on the composite were quite different from those obtained for the

epoxy resin and showed continuous cracking (Fig. 3b). The load increased linearly at first before settling down at a constant load during continuous crack growth. The load finally decreased sharply only when the crack reached the end of the specimen. This behaviour was identical in both water and paraffin.

V(K) Measurements

The relationship between V and K_{I} for the silica particle-filled epoxy resin in air is given in Fig. 4 in the form of a log-log plot. The data are mainly from load relaxation experiments and the symbols are explained in the figure caption. For the size of specimen used it was found that the slope (B) and the intercept (C) of the compliance calibration curve were $1.0 \pm 0.1 \times 10^{-5} \text{ N}^{-1}$ and $4.0 \pm 0.5 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mm.N}^{-1}$ respectively. It can be seen that all the data points fall approximately upon two intersecting straight lines. Above a crack velocity of about $10^{-6} \text{ m sec}^{-1}$, the $V(K)$ curve has a slope of about 60; below $10^{-6} \text{ m sec}^{-1}$ the slope is lower at about 35. It must also be noted that over the range of K_{I} investigated there appears to be no threshold value of K_{I} (or K_{I}^*) below which no crack growth occurred.

Environmental effects

Some preliminary experiments on slow crack growth in silica particle-filled epoxy resin in distilled water and paraffin were carried out using the DT specimen. The effect of environment upon the shape of the $V(K)$ diagram is shown in Fig. 5. The bimodal curve from Fig. 4 is also present with the data points deleted. In water the crack velocities are increased by nearly an order of magnitude whereas in paraffin the velocities are reduced by more than the same amount. The effects of water and paraffin on slow crack growth in the composite are analogous to the effects they have on the fracture of pure glass (11,12).

Microscopy

Figure 6 is a photograph of the fracture surface of a DT specimen of the composite. In this area two load relaxation tests have been carried out and the curved nature of the crack front can be seen. The arrow indicates the direction of crack growth. At the beginning of the test the fracture surface has a light appearance and as the crack slows down the surface becomes darker. It was found from constant load and constant displacement rate tests using DT specimens that the light surface was typical of areas where the crack velocity was greater than about $10^{-6} \text{ m sec}^{-1}$; at $V < 10^{-6} \text{ m sec}^{-1}$ the surface took on a dark appearance. Figure 7 shows Steroscan photomicrographs of the two types of fracture

surface. In the 'fast' area ($V > 10^{-6}$ m sec $^{-1}$) it is difficult to differentiate between the glass particles and the epoxy resin since the crack appears to have propagated through both the filler and the matrix. In the 'slow' area ($V < 10^{-6}$ m sec $^{-1}$) the surface is much rougher and silica particles can be seen protruding from the fracture surface of the matrix. There are also gaps around the particles as a result of interfacial failure between the silica and the epoxy resin. This difference between 'fast' and 'slow' fracture can be considered analogous to transgranular and intergranular failure in metals.

A fracture surface of the pure epoxy resin examined at the same magnification as the surface of the composite appeared to be perfectly smooth.

Time-to-failure predictions

The relationship between V and K_{I} can be used to predict the life-time, ψ_f , of a component where ψ_f is controlled by subcritical (slow) crack growth. It has been shown that for the composite, V is unique function of K_{I} at a given temperature and a given environment.

The time-to-failure, ψ_f , at constant stress is given by the integral

$$\psi_f = \int_{a_i}^{a_c} \frac{1}{V(K_I)} da \quad (6)$$

where a_i is the initial crack size and a_c is the crack size at which the crack becomes unstable. Using the definition of stress intensity factor, K_I :

$$K_I = \sigma_a Y \sqrt{a} \quad (7)$$

where Y is a geometrical factor (equal to $\sqrt{\pi}$ for infinitely wide specimens) and σ_a is the applied stress, then

$$\psi_f = \frac{2}{\sigma_a^2 Y^2} \int_{K_{Ii}}^{K_{If}} \frac{K_I}{V(K_I)} dK_I \quad (8)$$

where K_{Ii} is the initial value of K_I and K_{If} is the final value of

K_{Ii} . Thus,

$$\Psi_f = \frac{2 [(K_{Ii}^{2-n} - K_{If}^{2-n})]}{[(n-2) A Y^2 \sigma_a^2]} \quad (9)$$

If we assume instantaneous fracture to occur when the final stress intensity factor, K_{If} , reaches K_{IC} , the plane strain fracture toughness, then the time-to-failure is given by:

$$\psi_f = \frac{2 [(K_{Ii}^{2-n} - K_{IC}^{2-n})]}{[(n-2) A Y^2 \sigma_a^2]} \quad (10)$$

If n is large and $K_{Ii} < 0.9 K_{IC}$, equation (12) can be written approximately as:

$$\psi_f \approx \left[\frac{2 K_{Ii}^{(2-n)}}{(n-2) A Y^2 \sigma_a^2} \right] \quad (11)$$

Figure 8 gives experimentally measured time-to-failure values for unnotched tensile specimens of the composite held at various constant stress levels (σ) at 22 °C and 60 °C (14). The predicted times-to-failure, ψ_f , have also been plotted in Fig. 8 for different values of a_i , the initial flaw size. It may be seen that within experimental error most of the measured values fall within the predictions for $100 \mu\text{m} < a_i < 150 \mu\text{m}$. The large spread in the measured times-to-failure appears to reflect the variation in the initial (inherent) flaw size in the composite. In Fig. 4 measurements of $V(K)$ have only been made for values of K_I greater than about $1.5 \text{ MNm}^{-3/2}$. This means that time-to-failure predictions can only be made with any degree of certainty for values of K_{Ii} above $1.5 \text{ MNm}^{-3/2}$. The dashed sections of the lines in Fig. 8 are therefore the time-to-failure predictions obtained by assuming that the curve in the $V(K)$ diagram (Fig. 4) may be extrapolated linearly to velocities lower than the ones actually measured.

Discussion

Toughening mechanisms

Table 1 gives the fracture surface energy γ_s , plane strain fracture toughness, K_{IC} and Young's Modulus, E , for pure resin, the composite investigated in this work and silica glass (15).

	CT200/ HT901 (1)	CT 200/HT 901 + 46% silica flour	Silica (16) Glass
γ_s (Jm^{-2})	120	250 \pm 50	4.4
K_{IC} ($\text{MNm}^{-3/2}$)	0.86	2.2 \pm 0.1	0.79
E (GNm^{-2})	3.1	10 \pm 1	72

Table 1. Variation of fracture surface energy γ_s , fracture toughness K_{IC} and Young's modulus E for the pure epoxy resin, the resin filled with silica flour and pure silica glass.

γ_s has been calculated for the composite using the relation

$$K_{IC} = \sqrt{\frac{2E_c \gamma_s}{(1 - \nu^2)}} \quad (\text{under plane strain conditions}) \quad (12)$$

The Young's modulus of the composite, E_c , was calculated using the specimen dimensions and the slope of the compliance calibration curve (B) through the relation

$$E_c = \left(\frac{6 W_m^2 (1 + \nu)}{W t^3 B} \right) \quad (13)$$

K_{IC} for the composite has again been taken as the maximum measured value of K_I (Fig. 4). It is clear from Table 1 that the composite is tougher than either of the two components; γ_s for the filled system is about 250 Jm^{-2} which is over twice that of the pure resin and sixty times that of silica glass.

Several research workers (1,2,4,5-8) have attempted to isolate the strengthening mechanisms in brittle solids filled with brittle second phase particles. Three main proposals have been put forward to explain this phenomenon:

- (1) an increase in surface area due to crack branching that leads to an increase in the measured fracture surface energy;
- (2) plastic deformation of the matrix around the second phase particles; and
- (3) an increase in the line energy of the crack front as a result of crack bowing due to pinning by the second phase obstacles. This is analogous to the 'line tension effect' in dislocation pinning in metals.

Detailed investigation of these mechanisms has been carried out by varying the particle volume fraction size (1-9). It seems from these investigations that there is no one universal toughening mechanism for all composite systems. Clearly the first mechanism must increase the measured value of γ_s and this effect must always be present when the fracture surface of the composite is rougher than that of the pure material. However, it is doubtful that this mechanism alone can account for the measured increase in γ_s (2). It is known that under certain conditions, materials that are thought to be brittle will undergo plastic deformation. Glass for example will flow under a hardness indenter (15) and epoxy resins yield and flow in compression tests (16). Lilley (1) considered that in epoxy resins filled with second phase particles local plastic deformation around the particles was responsible for the increase in γ_s and he discounted the third mechanism. By varying volume fraction and particle size Lange (6) showed that in a sodium borosilicate glass - Al_2O_3 system the increase in γ_s could be more satisfactorily explained by considering the interaction of the crack front with the second phase dispersion, although there was also an increase in γ_s because of surface roughness. Evans (7) showed that increases in strength would be expected for a brittle matrix containing second phase brittle particles because of a 'line tension effect.' He showed this effect would be important at high volume fractions (i.e. small interparticle spacings).

Microfailure processes

An important feature that has been brought to light in this present work is the dependence of fracture behaviour of the composite on the crack velocity and environment. The microfailure processes at the crack tip in the composite may be affected by a localised concentration of a chemical species (such as moisture) in the environment. The chemical species can therefore influence the failure processes by affecting (1) plastic deformation in the epoxy resin, (2) surface energy of the silica particles and epoxy resin and (3) interfacial bond energy between the silica and matrix. However, there is no available data at present to establish whether or not water vapour in the atmosphere has influenced

these surface energy terms to any great extent. It can only be suggested that water may have affected these surface energy terms and interfacial bond energy to the extent that the mode of crack propagation is a function of the rate of reaction and crack velocity.

Crack velocity and environmental effects

The V(K) diagram for the silica-epoxy resin composite shows the overall crack growth rate is composed of at least two elementary microfailure processes composed of transparticle and interparticle fracture. At $V < 10^{-6}$ m sec⁻¹ failure occurs by fracture through the silica particles and the curve has a slope (n) of about 60; at $V > 10^{-6}$ m sec⁻¹ crack propagation occurs by particle-matrix debonding and particle pull-out, and the slope (n) of the curve is about 35. The overall rate of crack growth will therefore be determined by an activation energy spectrum for the overall reaction between the composite and moisture in the environment. This activation energy spectrum may exhibit discrete values each associated with one of the specific rate-controlling elementary reactions or breakdown of the silica-epoxy resin interface. At the intersection of these two curves at $V_T = 10^{-6}$ m sec⁻¹ (Fig. 4), the individual rates of reaction between environment and silica, or environment and interface, are equal; elsewhere, one step will have a rate significantly different to the other. The overall crack propagation rate in the composite will therefore depend on the reaction kinetics of the overall reaction between material and environment.

It is highly likely that the transition between transparticle fracture and interparticle failure will be affected by surface treatment of the silica particles. If the particle-matrix bond was strengthened, the pulling out of particles should be inhibited; with a weak bond particle fracture should not occur. A strong bond should therefore improve the long term properties where crack velocities are low ($< 10^{-6}$ m sec⁻¹); conversely, weakly-bonded particles should increase the impact resistance of the composite where crack velocities are greater than 10^{-6} m sec⁻¹.

It is interesting to note that the effects of water and paraffin on the growth of cracks in the composite are analogous to the effect that these environments have upon crack propagation in glass (11,12). Since the composite consists of 46% by volume of silica glass, it is not surprising that its fracture behaviour in wet and dry environments is similar to that of glass in the same environments.

Inherent flaw size

The strength of a structural material is governed by the size

of the largest inherent flaw that exists in the component. Analysis of the time-to-failure data in section 4 has shown that the critical inherent flaw size (a_0) in the unnotched creep rupture specimens was of the order of 100-150 μm . We must now consider what microstructural features would give rise to flaws of this size. In the silica-filled epoxy resin over 50% of the particles are between 64 and 74 μm in diameter, although it is known that particles greater than this size do exist. The interparticle spacing, d , can be estimated from the equation (2).

$$d = \left(\frac{2D(1-V_f)}{3V_f} \right) \quad (14)$$

where D is the average particle diameter and V_f is the volume fraction of silica in the composite. For a composite with V_f equal to 0.46 and D equal to 70 μm then d is 55 μm which corresponds to about one half of the average size of the predicted inherent flaws. It is known that a range of particle sizes and therefore, a distribution of interparticle spacings exists in the composite. From these simple estimations of inherent flaw size we can only conclude at the present time that a_0 is equivalent to the largest

(1) crack in the matrix between particles, (2) fractured particle, or (3) debonded silica particle due to interfacial failure. An increase in the strength of the composite should therefore be obtained by reducing the average silica particle size and interparticle spacing in the composite.

Conclusions and Implications

Previous investigations into the fracture behaviour of composite materials consisting of brittle second phase particles in a brittle matrix have shown that the fracture behaviour of the composite is affected by composition, particle size and particle surface treatment. This present investigation has shown that the behaviour is also affected by crack velocity and environment. It has been found that the crack velocity (V) is a unique function of the stress intensity factor (K_I) at the tip of the crack. In water the crack velocity is increased by a factor of 8 whereas in paraffin the velocity is reduced by over an order of magnitude.

Two distinct failure mechanisms have been identified. In air at crack velocities in excess of 10^{-6} m sec^{-1} , failure takes place mainly by means of particle fracture; at crack velocities below this value failure takes place primarily by interfacial break-down and particle pull-out. This change in failure mechanism is accompanied by a transition in the $V(K)$ diagram at about 10^{-6} m sec^{-1} . Using the $V(K)$ relationship and time-to-failure data obtained from creep rupture experiments, it has been possible to estimate the size of the inherent flaw present in the composite

to be between 100 and 150 μm .

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1. A schematic representation of a $V(K)$ diagram for a brittle material that exhibits environmental crack growth.

2. A schematic representation of the DT specimen. (The shaded area represents fracture surface area).

(a)

(b)

3. Load-time curves for Double Torsion specimens, a) epoxy resin in air, b) filled resin in water.

4. Crack velocity (da/dt) as a function of stress intensity factor (K_I) for the filled resin in air. The different symbols are from relaxation tests on different specimens. The three larger symbols are from constant displacement rate tests or direct measurements of crack velocity.

5. Crack velocity (da/dt) as a function of K_I for the filled resin in paraffin and distilled water measured using the relaxation method. The lines are taken from Fig. 2, and the larger symbols refer to constant displacement rate tests.

6. A fracture surface of the filled resin obtained in air. In the area shown two relaxation tests have been carried out and the curved nature of the crack front can be seen. The arrow indicates the direction of crack growth.

25 μ m

"FAST"

25 μ m

"SLOW"

7. Scanning electron photomicrographs of a fracture surface of the filled epoxy resin obtained in air. In the 'fast' area the crack was growing faster than 10^{-6} m sec $^{-1}$ and in the 'slow' area the crack velocity was less than 10^{-6} m sec $^{-1}$.

8. Creep rupture data for the filled resin at 22°C in air (14). The two solid lines have been calculated from the measured $V(K)$ relationship in Fig. 4 using values of inherent flaw size of 100 μm and 150 μm . The curves have been extended with dashed lines by assuming that the $V(K)$ relationship can be extrapolated to velocities lower than those actually measured.